

Tobephobia: Teachers' Ineptitude to Manage Curriculum Change

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Abstract—In this paper, Tobephobia (TBP) alludes to the fear of failure experienced by teachers to manage curriculum change. TBP is an emerging concept and it extends the boundaries of research in terms of how we view achievement and failure in education. Outcomes-based education (OBE) was introduced fifteen years ago in South African schools without simultaneously upgrading teachers' professional competencies. This exploratory research, therefore examines a simple question: What is the impact of TBP and OBE on teachers? Teacher ineptitude to cope with the OBE curriculum in the classroom is a serious problem affecting large numbers of South African teachers. This exploratory study sought to determine the perceived negative impact of OBE and TBP on teachers. A survey was conducted amongst 311 teachers in Port Elizabeth and Durban, South Africa. The results confirm the very negative impact of TBP and OBE on teachers. This exploratory study authenticates the existence of TBP.

Keywords—Curriculum change, fear of failure in education, outcomes-based education, Tobephobia.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is obvious that school-based curricula are provided to learners by their teachers, making the teacher's role paramount to the effective implementation of the curriculum. What to teach, and how to teach the contents, are inextricably intertwined in the way curriculum planning, implementation, and assessment take place. Teacher training is undoubtedly essential for the effective implementation in schools of any innovative curriculum [27]. Multiple studies consistently indicate that when teacher training is overlooked, or is ineffective, then this would result in the implementation failure of curriculum change [27, 41, 42]. Quality education is therefore dependent on well-resourced schools and effective teaching by suitably qualified teachers. The chasm in education will deepen, when inconsistencies in teachers' competencies to deliver quality education in their classrooms surface, and become more pronounced, during the curriculum implementation phase.

Outcomes-based education (OBE) was implemented in South Africa in 1998. It was based on the principles of democracy, human rights, ubuntu and social justice and required high levels of academic skills from teachers [28]. One of the major flaws in the implementation of OBE was the lack of adequate in-service training of teachers. A haphazard

approach of facilitating disjointed workshops, to a small percentage of teachers, would hardly address the enormity of the training of teachers required to manage curriculum change. Teachers really had no clarity as to what was required of them [30]. Even in the Report of the Task Team [12] which reviewed the implementation of the National Curriculum Statement [NCS], it was unanimously stated "that current teacher policies to support the curriculum are often too generic and superficial and did not provide the needed support to teachers." The Department of Education (South Africa) admitted that addressing the need to develop teachers' professional competencies to usher in curriculum changes would not be appropriate with a *one size fits all* approach [12]. This still remains a major challenge to the Department, in its in-service training programme of teachers.

The OBE curriculum was not based on sound research for implementation in South Africa; there was inadequate preparation and consideration of whether teachers were prepared sufficiently for such a fundamental curriculum change [12]. The lack of teachers' knowledge of curriculum content, led to fear of failure which over-shadowed their motivation to achieve desired educational outcomes [41]. Comparative studies done by Donnelly [14] in Australia and South Africa point out that the learning outcomes in OBE are vague, ambiguous, difficult to measure, and low in academic content. His findings support other research studies on this subject that OBE represents a dumbed-down approach to standards, because of the lack of academic rigour, and the lack of a strong, clearly articulated educational justification or research evidence proving the success or worth of OBE [27].

Research shows that there is a lack of a clearly articulated educational justification for OBE, or even plausible evidence to prove its success [12, 14, 1, 7, 13]. This research confirms that the implementation of the curriculum changes without the relevant resources to teach it, would cause stress and strain leading to dire consequences and impacting on the teachers' morale to implement the planned curriculum changes [12, 14, 42]. A major hurdle for these teachers is to teach the content without being properly trained to do so. Teachers' inability to implement the NCS resulted in them suffering from emotional dissonance. This inevitably caused them to experience ineptitude and insurmountable fears of failure, and hence not realise educational aims and objectives.

According to Ginsberg and Lyche [22], it seems clear that "rising interest and negative feelings have taken hold and that a culture of fear has emerged concerning issues of public education." This can be attributed to teachers' incompetence

to facilitate curriculum change such as the OBE curriculum due to inadequate, or no professional development of their knowledge and skills. Consequently, their fear of failure will make it simply easier for them to continue teaching in the traditional way, thus maintaining the status quo [24]. This fear to achieve desired educational outcomes is appropriately conceptualised as *Tobephobia* (TBP) [41, 42].

Studies [42, 43] affirm that teachers' lack of professional competencies can result in them experiencing untold levels of anxiety, stress and tension. Curriculum change that is incompatible with teachers' knowledge and skills would in all likelihood be met with resistance from them [42]. It would therefore not be unexpected for them to maintain their status quo, regarding their traditional teaching practices, a reaction emanating from their fear of failure, which is manifested in the emerging concept of TBP [42].

This exploratory research therefore examines a simple question:

What is the impact of TBP and OBE on teachers?

This article will examine the perceptions of teachers' fears of being incompetent to teach effectively as a result of curriculum change associated with OBE.

II. TOBEPHOBIA AND CURRICULUM CHANGE

It is far from clear what it would mean to implement a curriculum for teachers who were not trained to implement the new curriculum, as this would inevitably result in significant decreases in learner performance [39]. Over the past fifteen years, major changes have taken place in the South African educational knowledge system, as it epitomizes the growing and changing educational needs of a developing country. The introduction of the OBE approach in South African schools led to a discrepancy between the teachers' knowledge of the traditional curriculum and the principles of the OBE curriculum [44].

Adoption of the OBE approach was not an easy passage for most teachers to manage, given the level of knowledge in education, in South Africa. Lack of resources and inadequate professional development and training were, and still are, one of the major challenges facing teachers in transforming the educational system. Not having the capacity to usher in the changes at classroom level, has led to untold levels of anxiety, stress and tension within the teaching community [42]. These developments have contributed to the existence of a phobia in the educational environment [40, 41], and in terms of the evidence gathered, by the researcher over the past decade, this fear of failure was aptly named *Tobephobia* (TBP). Therefore, in this study, curriculum change as a contributory factor to TBP was investigated.

New approaches to education that had been implemented without the relevant training of teachers meant many were "thrown in at the deep end" without a clue of exactly what to do. *Tobephobia* simply means the *fear of failure* to achieve the objectives of teaching and learning in education [42]. Initially, TBP referred to the fears experienced by teachers in the

implementation of the OBE curriculum, but over the past decade, the word (*Tobephobia*) has expanded to cover the broader issues of fear experienced within the educational environment. In this paper, *Tobephobia* (TBP) alludes to the fear of failure experienced by teachers to manage curriculum change.

In the *APA Dictionary of Psychology* [49], phobia is defined as:

... a persistent and irrational fear of a specific situation, object, or activity (e.g., heights, dogs, water, blood, driving, flying), which is consequently either strenuously avoided or endured with marked distress.

Phobia denotes a morbid dread of anything and is used especially as a suffix to describe a specific experience of fear, such as TBP [9]. Phobic dysfunctions affect not only the patient but also the people around them [20]. Phobic people spend most of their time worrying about their fears and tend to be too frightened, to attend to their normal daily chores [20].

Evidently, fear abounds in the educational environment when teachers fail to teach their learners what is expected of them [21]. Newkirk [35] asserts that for teachers, their professional identity "is bound up in their teaching success; when they fail, something very precious can be put at risk." He notes that difficulty, disappointment, resistance, and failures are inevitable, in the teaching profession. Definitely, some failure is a natural consequence of the tremendous challenges teachers take on in their schools [47]. Lack of manageable workloads, the expansion of the curriculum and a lack of continuous skill development; have been cited by Conley and Glasman [10] as sources of fear experienced by teachers. When widely publicised questions emerge about the relevance of the curriculum and the ability of teachers to teach it, then uncertainty and fear of failure would be inevitable outcomes.

Teachers feel threatened by the prospect of change in the curriculum [53]. Their acceptance of curriculum change, could be affected by perceived threats to their expertise and proven abilities, and their belief that they lack the professional competence to implement curriculum change, successfully [24, 18]. As pointed out by Zimmerman [53], "teachers and others who benefit from the current distribution and control of resources might perceive *threats to their resource allocations* brought about by changes in the school." Kealey, Peterson, Gaul, and Dinh [27] also observed, that teacher training conceptualized as a positive behaviour change process, can promote effective implementation of curriculum change in school classrooms, if it leads to the upgrading of teachers' knowledge and skills. The converse is also true.

The professional incompetence of teachers to successfully implement the planned curriculum in their classrooms has a negative bearing on learning outcomes [33]. Research shows that learners taught by incompetent teachers experience cognitive dissonance, resulting in lasting decreased achievement [11, 38, 26, 48, 34]. There is ample evidence that poor teaching materially contributes to higher levels of failure rates amongst learners [19]. The matriculation results in South

Africa bear testimony to the professional incompetence of teachers to teach effectively. Approximately two out of every five learners, who were enrolled in the 2009 matriculation examinations failed: a total of 217 331 of the 551 940 candidates who sat for the examinations – just under 40% - failed [46]. As reported in the *Sunday Times* [46], poor teaching and weak management of schools have been blamed for this mediocre pass rate and the Minister of Basic Education (Angie Motshekga) has vowed to crack down on the poor quality of teaching at schools in South Africa. When widely publicized questions emerge about our failing educational system, then uncertainty and fear are inevitable outcomes [22, 23]. TBP drains teachers of their motivation and inspiration and it prevents them from realising their full potential, as it impacts negatively on them personally, their teaching, on learners and on the teaching profession.

Several researchers [52, 38] report that the quality of teaching over a period of three years can make significant differences in the learners' test scores translating into as much as 50 to 60 percentile points. Based on their research findings, these authors contend that "the most important factor affecting student learning is the teacher" and that "if the teacher is ineffective, students under that teacher's tutelage, will achieve inadequate progress academically." Due to the fact that these teachers affect all their learners who they come into contact with, it is imperative that the Department of Education needs to do more to protect these learners from incompetently trained teachers [33].

III. FEAR OF FAILURE IN EDUCATION

In the *APA Dictionary of Psychology* [49], the fear of failure is explained as follows:

...persistent and irrational anxiety about failing to measure up to the standards and goals set by oneself or others. This may include anxiety over academic standing, losing a job, sexual inadequacy, or loss of face and self-esteem.

Prompted by the pioneering research by Atkinson [3, 4], researchers have studied the converse of achievement motivation, namely the fear of failure in education [45]. Birney, Burdick and Teevan's [8] theory on the fear of failure, indicates that individuals attempt to escape from achievement-oriented situations because of their fear of failure in those situations. For teachers, the fear is also associated with curriculum mandates [21]. Spitzer [45] asserts that the need for achievement and fear of failure, have been shown to be orthogonal to each other. Spitzer's [45] study found that the following characteristics lead to high levels of fear of failure and insecurity amongst teachers:

- Lack of teacher effectiveness.
- Teachers being subjected to continual criticism, with little praise.
- Lack of validated competencies.
- Lack of collegial co-operation.

Teaching is an intricate and challenging occupation and research confirms that, in recent years, it has become part of

one of the "high stress" ranked professions [15, 29, 20]. The fear of failure in education can lead teachers to [40]:

- Have a low self-esteem and lack of motivation.
- Lose their passion to teach.
- Become indifferent to innovations in education.
- Leave the profession.

For teachers, TBP is a fear of being incompetent to carry out their professional obligations in a disabling educational environment [43].

IV. PROFESSIONAL INCOMPETENCE OF TEACHERS TO COPE WITH CURRICULUM CHANGES

Studies [25, 31, 50] conducted on retaining incompetent teachers, indicate that such teachers have a negative influence on staff morale by exuding negativity and having poor collegial relations. Once teachers are permanently appointed, the dismissal of incompetent teachers becomes a difficult process [2, 16, 17, 51].

An analysis of the three obstacles of getting teachers involved in curriculum change is evident, when viewed in terms of their perspective as pointed out below [36]:

1. *Lack of ownership.* Much of the current demand to implement the NCS to transform the curriculum is stemming from the National Government in South Africa; hence teachers are not readily accepting this top-down approach from an external source.
2. *Differential knowledge.* Teachers tend to feel frustrated that their power base has been eroded by those external forces imposing change in the school, without concurrently putting into place supporting infrastructure.
3. *Sudden wholesale change.* Curriculum change was introduced in South Africa without simultaneously upgrading the knowledge and skills of teachers, to teach the new curriculum. Most of these teachers suffer from acute bouts of a sense of failure, because of a lack of proper training.

Balt [5] contends that all the problems of curriculum change in South Africa have their origins in the way that OBE was initially conceptualised and the generally poor quality of teacher training. As pointed out by Kealey et al. [27], the goal of any in-service training should be behavioural – that teachers implement the curriculum as designed. According to them, the four objectives of teacher training to implement curriculum change should be to [27]:

1. Motivate teachers to want to teach the curriculum.
2. Communicate implementation responsibilities to teachers.
3. Furnish teachers with all the materials essential for successful implementation of the curriculum.
4. Help teachers gain the information, skills, and confidence needed, to successfully implement the curriculum.

A prerequisite to acquiring knowledge and skills, is that teachers must be motivated to implement curriculum change. Motivating teachers to want to implement the curriculum, must be a training priority. As aptly explained by Kealey et al. [27], clear and complete communication of responsibilities is

a vital in-service objective that must include all implementation procedures and special teaching requirements, as well as guidelines, for curriculum modification that can be made to accommodate teaching styles and classroom needs.

Objectives three and four recommended by Kealey et al. [27] are particularly important to develop the professional competence of teachers, to implement curriculum change in their classrooms. Providing essential materials allows teachers to focus their attention on teaching their learners, rather than tracking down materials they do not have. This removes the potential for implementation failure. To avoid the effects of professional incompetence of teachers to implement curriculum change, in-service training must not only empower them to acquire knowledge and skills required by the curriculum, but also build their confidence in working with unfamiliar subjects and teaching styles.

V. PURPOSE

For learners to benefit maximally from teaching, it is imperative that teachers are suitably trained to teach the curriculum effectively and that teachers experience adequate levels of that aspect of their job satisfaction. Two of the factors that may jeopardize teaching are OBE with its emphasis on curriculum change and teachers' fear of failure, as expressed in TBP. Curriculum implementation failure is a common problem experienced by teachers when they lack the knowledge and skills to teach the subject matter. Policy statements do not easily feed into the practice of teaching. The purpose of this study was thus to establish teachers' perceptions of the negative impact of OBE and TBP on teaching and to determine to what extent these two concepts are related.

VI. METHOD

A. Research Design

A multi-respondent survey design was used in this study [37].

B. Participants

The subjects chosen to participate in the study were selected following a process described by McMillan and Schumacher [32] as non-probability convenience sampling, because the subjects were selected on the basis of their accessibility and availability. Hence, for the purpose of this study, the participants were teachers studying at the Nelson Mandela Metropolitan University (NMMU) in 2009. Ethics clearance to proceed with the study, was granted by the institution (NMMU).

There was also an element of stratified sampling used [32]. Hence, the final sample was neither random, nor probability based. It was a mixture of convenience and stratified sampling and this ensured that the population represented a cross-section of teachers, at all post levels. The questionnaires were completed by teachers from Port Elizabeth and Durban. Although the subjects were used to generate comparative results, it was also important to ensure that the sample was not

biased and that it represented teachers from urban and rural areas (see Table I). Due to the fact that the main NMMU campus is based in Port Elizabeth, 78.8% of the respondents were from this site.

C. Procedure

Two NMMU sites in Durban and Port Elizabeth, were used to obtain a representative sample of the teachers in these regions. Lecturers and tutors at these two pre-selected sites assisted to distribute and collect the questionnaires. This was accomplished over a period of three months. For ethical reasons, respondents were advised not to disclose their names or the names of their schools on the questionnaire. Confidentiality and anonymity were thus ensured and the participation of the respondents was on a totally voluntary basis. Of the 335 questionnaires distributed, 311 completed questionnaires were returned. This represented a return rate of 92,8%.

D. Questionnaire

The structured questionnaire was initially compiled by the author of this study. An extensive literature review on achievement motivation and the fear of failure experienced by teachers was undertaken, in the first stage of developing the questionnaire. This first draft copy was then subjected to further review and modification by a qualified statistician at NMMU. Thereafter, the second draft copy of the questionnaire was critically reviewed by four teachers, two principals, an academic with curriculum specialization, and an educational psychologist. Their critical input was duly considered, in finalizing the questionnaire for this study. This process ensured the face validity and the content validity of the measuring instrument used for the research.

The questionnaire was divided into two sections as follows:

- Section A: The demographic variables of the participant
- Section B: A Tobophobia inventory.

Section B covered nine areas, including the causes of TBP and the social incompetence of principals. However, in terms of the delimitation and focus of this article, the two sub-sections in the questionnaire that will be addressed in this article are sub-section 6, which focused on the perceptions of the negative impact of TBP on teachers' job satisfaction; and sub-section 10, which focused on the impact of OBE on current teaching.

In sub-section 6, respondents were required to respond to six questions with three options: agree fully (A+), agree partially (A-), or disagree (D). In sub-section 10, the respondents also had to consider a level of perceived impact with options: major (M+), minor (M-), or none (N). Summated scores were calculated for each of the sub-sections in section B of the questionnaire by mapping the average of the relevant items ranging from 1 (A+/M+) to 3 (D/N) to a score between 0 (Vey low negative impact) to 100 (very high negative impact). Cronbach's alpha coefficient values were

used, to determine the reliability (internal consistency) of the summated scores.

E. Data Analysis

The data analysis was done by a qualified statistician at NMMU. Descriptive statistics were used to summarise the sample statistics, while inferential tests were conducted to investigate the significance of relationships among variables. Inferential test results were deemed significant if they were both statistically significant at the $\alpha = .05$ level and also practically significant according to the guidelines for the relevant test.

VII. RESULTS

The characteristics of the respondents are summarised in Table I to reflect the representativeness of the sample whilst the responses to the items relating to the impact of TBP and OBE on teaching are summarised in Tables II and III.

TABLE I
RESPONDENTS' CHARACTERISTICS (N = 311)

Site	Gender		
Port Elizabeth	78.8%	Male	35.7%
Durban	21.2%	Female	64.3%
Post Level	Grades and Phases		
Teacher	69.5%	1-3	15.8%
Head of Department	14.5%	4-6	19.6%
Deputy Principal	3.2%	7-9	36.3%
Principal	11.6%	10-12	48.6%
Other	1.6%	other	3.5%
Age	Years Teaching Experience		
20-29	13.5%	0-2	8.4%
30-39	18.0%	3-4	4.8%
40-49	44.7%	5-9	10.0%
50-59	22.2%	10-19	38.3%
60+	1.6%	20+	38.6%
School Type			
Ex-Model C School	19.6%		
Section 21 Urban State School	45.3%		
Section 21 Rural State School	4.8%		

Independent School	12.2%
Non-section 21 Urban State School	12.2%
Non-section 21 Rural State School	3.2%
Farm School	2.6%

TABLE II
FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION: SUB-SECTION 6 ITEMS RELATING TO THE IMPACT OF TBP ON TEACHERS' JOB SATISFACTION (N = 311)

	Agree Fully	Agree partially	Disagree
TBP has a negative impact on the self-esteem of teachers.	77%	21%	2%
Teachers are demotivated as a result of TBP.	76%	23%	1%
Teachers develop a negative attitude towards their job because of TBP	75%	23%	2%
TBP results in teachers disliking their job	72%	26%	2%
TBP leads to pessimism experienced by teachers	70%	27%	3%
Teachers have low expectations as a result of TBP	68%	29%	3%

TABLE III
FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION: SUB-SECTION 10 ITEMS RELATING TO THE IMPACT OF OBE ON CURRENT TEACHING (N = 311)

	Major	Minor	None
Increase in administrative tasks erodes the quality teaching time of teachers	85%	13%	2%
Teachers are not professionally trained to teach the new curriculum	71%	23%	6%
OBE is all about the stakeholders and not the teachers	58%	33%	9%
Anyone and everyone is expected to teach anything at any time.	55%	24%	21%
Teachers are stripped of their traditional role to impart knowledge	51%	33%	16%
Teachers' positions have been downgraded to being facilitators	49%	40%	11%
Teachers have lost their authority in the classrooms.	48%	40%	12%

From Table II it is clear that the majority of the respondents were fully in agreement regarding the negative impact of TBP on teachers' job satisfaction, ranging between approximately 2 out of 3 (68%) to 3 out of 4 (77%) for the six items.

The results in Table III indicate greater variability with regard to the impact of OBE on teaching, compared to that for the impact of TBP, on teachers' job satisfaction. The largest proportion of the sample perceived OBE as having a major negative impact on teaching, ranging between almost half (48%) to 85% of the respondents for the seven items.

The observed Cronbach's coefficients alpha values of 0.91 and 0.87 respectively, for the summated scores measuring the negative impact of TBP and OBE on teachers were much higher than 0.70, the minimum value regarded as significant, thus confirming the scores' reliability.

Descriptive statistics for the summated scores measuring the negative impact of TBP and OBE on teachers are reflected in Table IV.

High mean scores of 85.23 and 74.22 were observed for TBP and OBE factors respectively on a scale ranging from 0 (very low negative impact) to 100 (very high negative impact). Approximately half (51%) the respondents obtained TBP scores ranging from 90 to 100, whilst just more than half (54%) obtained OBE scores of 75 or higher.

TABLE IV

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS FOR THE SCORES MEASURING THE NEGATIVE IMPACT OF TBP AND OBE ON TEACHERS (N = 311)

Score Interval	TBP		OBE	
	Percentage	Cumulative	Percentage	Cumulative
90-100	51%	51%	32%	32%
75-89	28%	79%	23%	54%
50-74	19%	98%	33%	87%
25-49	2	100%	11%	98%
10-24	0%	100%	1%	99%
0-9	0%	100%	1%	100%
Statistic				
Mean	85.23		74.22	
Std. Dev.	15.72		22.44	
Minimum	29.00		0.00	
Quartile 1	75.00		57.00	
Median	92.00		79.00	
Quartile 3	100.00		93.00	
Maximu m	100.00		100.00	

The results of analysis conducted to determine to what extent the negative impact of OBE on teachers is related to the negative impact of TBP on teachers' job satisfaction will now be presented.

Fig. 1 is a frequency scatterplot, depicting the relationship between the negative impacts of OBE with that of TBP. The observed Pearson Product Moment correlation value was .405 which was found to be significant ($r > .111$ the $\alpha = .05$ level threshold value level and also $r > .300$ the threshold value for moderate practical significance).

To further investigate the relationship between the impact of OBE and that of TBP on teachers, a Chi² test of independence was conducted based on the contingency table reflected in Table V.

Fig 1 The relationship between the negative impact of OBE on teachers with that of TBP

TABLE V

CONTINGENCY TABLE, DEPICTING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE NEGATIVE IMPACT OF OBE ON TEACHERS AND THAT OF TBP ON TEACHERS' JOB SATISFACTION

OBE	TBP			Total	
	Below Average	Average	Above Average		
Below Average	26	43%	13	21%	61
Average	35	20%	76	43%	178
Above Average	3	4%	49	68%	72
Total	64	21%	138	44%	311
chi ² (d.f. =4, n=311) = 41.87; p<0005; V = 0.26 Medium					

Given the observed significant positive correlation coefficients and the significant outcome of the Chi² test of independence, it can be concluded that in South African schools where the negative impact of OBE on teachers is high, it will typically be found that the negative impact of TBP on teachers' job satisfaction is also high.

VIII. DISCUSSION

Only 2% of the teachers disagreed, that TBP had a negative impact on their self – esteem as teachers. Ninety-nine percent of these teachers indicated that they suffer from demotivation as a result of TBP. Seventy-six percent of them, agreed fully to this statement. Ninety-eight percent of the teachers either agreed fully (75%) or agreed partially (23%) that they developed a negative attitude towards their job because of TBP and hence, only 2% and 3%, indicated that TBP had no impact on them liking their jobs or being optimistic about their job satisfaction respectively. The findings also confirmed that 97% of the teachers have low expectations regarding their job satisfaction.

Regarding the impact of OBE on teaching, 98% of the teachers believed that administrative tasks eroded their quality teaching time. Ninety-four percent of them believed that they were not professionally competent to teach the OBE curriculum. More than fifty percent of these teachers indicated that being asked to teach anything without having the basic training in the subject area had a detrimental impact on their ability to impart knowledge to their learners. Only 13% of the teachers felt that they retained their traditional authority in the classroom. The findings suggest that a total of 89% of the teachers, believed that OBE had either a major (49%) or minor (40%) impact on their traditional positions as teachers, indicating that their roles have been downgraded, to that of being mere facilitators in the instructional process.

IX. CONCLUSION

In this exploratory study, the high mean scores of 85.23 and 74.22 observed for the negative impact of OBE and TBP, confirm that these two variables had a very high negative impact on teachers. According to this finding and given the observed strong relationship between OBE and TBP, it can therefore be concluded that in South African schools, where the negative impact of curriculum change associated with OBE is high, it would be typically found that the negative impact of TBP on the teachers' job satisfaction would also be high. In dealing with TBP, it is of vital importance that teachers become aware of their fears, identify their ways in which they express fear, recognise the situations that trigger fear and use appropriate strategies to reduce fear and stress in their lives [6]. Effective training of teachers needs to take place on a continuous basis to sharpen their professional competencies and address these concerns. Implementing a curriculum without the adequate training of teachers, will diminish their chances of achievement and will engender fear regarding the outcomes in education. The problems associated with the implementation of the OBE curriculum should therefore serve as a benchmark when implementing the new curriculum based on Schooling 2025 in South Africa.

Given the large body of evidence in support of those opposing OBE, the Minister of Basic Education (in South Africa), has recently announced plans to phase out OBE and replace it with a schooling system that recognise the limitations of the South African society, for example that most South African children have limited or no access to the internet and to well-stocked libraries. The new education system will address *inter alia* the upgrading of school buildings and the training of teachers to equip them to teach the new curriculum [12].

The intention of this paper was to address the rationale that achievement motivation and the fear of failure in education are linked. The study has strongly suggested that teacher ineptitude to cope with curriculum change can have catastrophic consequences that can result in teachers suffering from stress, anxiety and tension, culminating in TBP. This exploratory study has succeeded to uncover the perceived

negative impact of OBE and TBP on teachers. Evidently, the results of the study confirm the very negative impact of TBP and OBE on teachers. Hence, this exploratory study authenticates the existence of TBP, as it relates to education. TBP is an emerging concept and it extends the boundaries of research in terms of how we view achievement and failure in education. Additional research needs to be done on TBP. Further research is required to investigate the causal relationship between the negative impact of constant curriculum change on teachers and the impact of TBP on their ability to continuously provide quality and equitable education to all learners.

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